

***In situ* high-temperature emissivity measurements of heat-treated, silicon coated stainless steel for solar thermal applications**

*Amrutha V.^{a,b}, Atasi Dan^c, Jon Gabirondo Lopez^d, Telmo Echaniz^d, Raquel Fuente^d, Harish
C. Barshilia^{a,b,*}, Gabriel Lopez^{d,*}*

^aAcademy of Scientific and Innovative Research (AcSIR), Ghaziabad, 201002, India

^bSurface Engineering Division, CSIR-National Aerospace Laboratories, Bangalore,
560017, India

^cDepartment of Physics, University of Colorado, Boulder, CO 80309, USA

^dUniversity of the Basque Country (UPV/EHU), Barrio Sarriena s/n, 48940 Leioa, Spain

*Corresponding author e-mail address: harish@nal.res.in, gabrielalejandro.lopez@ehu.eus

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ABSTRACT

Understanding thermal emissivity at high temperatures is crucial for developing efficient materials for solar thermal applications. We present a new approach for creating an efficient material for solar absorber by developing a nano structured surface on stainless steel substrate through Si deposition and annealing. We prepare five samples by annealing them at five temperatures between 700 °C and 1100 °C. Afterwards, we perform a systematic study of the spectral emissivity at elevated temperatures, focusing on different parameters: angle

dependence, wavelength dependence, and temperature dependence. The spectral directional emissivity experiments performed in the mid-infrared range reveal a dielectric behavior of the samples in the short wavelength region ($\lambda < 6 \mu\text{m}$) and metallic behavior in the long wavelength region ($\lambda > 12 \mu\text{m}$). The results indicate an increase in hemispherical and total normal emissivity with measurement temperature (from 200 °C to 700 °C), influenced by oxide/silicide formation due to interdiffusion, and by surface roughness. Notably, samples annealed at 900 °C and 1000 °C demonstrate enhanced thermal stability at 700 °C, showcasing promising characteristics for high-temperature applications. Consequently, this study presents a viable method for developing cost-effective silicon-based solar absorber coatings on stainless steel with tailored properties for solar thermal applications along with its real time high temperature emissivity details.

1. Introduction

Solar energy harvesting is of utmost importance due to the increasing climate change concerns and the depletion of non-renewable fuel sources. Concentrating solar thermal collectors play a crucial role in converting solar energy into thermal energy by means of spectrally selective solar absorbers (SSAs), and they will be crucial to make real the potential advantages of this technology, i.e., high efficiency, flexibility to mitigate intermittence, ease to be integrated with other technologies [1,2]. The SSAs should have high absorptivity (α) in the spectral range from 0.25 μm to 2.50 μm and low emissivity (ϵ) from 2.5 μm to 25 μm to minimize thermal radiation losses [3–5]. Those systems demonstrate heightened efficiency levels when operating at elevated temperatures, particularly surpassing 400 °C [6]. In recent years, there has been a growing interest in the development of novel spectrally selective absorbing materials having different designs and being fabricated using a variety of techniques [6–9].

Among SSAs, textured surfaces with their robust engineered structures have shown high absorptivity through mechanisms such as plasmonic effect, diffraction, multiple internal reflections or dipole scattering [10–13]. While these mechanisms offer enhanced solar absorption properties, they often rely on expensive techniques due to factors such as size of the structure, spacing of those nanostructures, orientation, and roughness of the surface [14–17]. In contrast, a cost-effective approach involves a controlled thermal treatment to induce microstructural changes at the surface, resulting in the creation of the desired textures [18,19]. That method offers an economically viable and scalable solution for widespread solar energy applications.

At high operating temperatures, textured surfaces are also vulnerable to degradation, including oxidation, material interdiffusion, surface roughness alterations, contaminant

deposition, and microstructural changes [17,20–22]. The infrared emissivity of a surface is a crucial parameter to characterize thermal radiation from the absorber, and it can be significantly affected by those transformations on textured absorber surfaces. The emissivity of coatings can be influenced by a combination of various crucial factors, including temperature, thickness, surface state (such as surface roughness and periodicity), and chemical composition. In concentrating solar power systems with an operating temperature exceeding 400 °C, there is a notable increase in radiative loss from absorber coatings. This increase is attributed to the fourth power dependence on temperature according to Stefan-Boltzmann's law. Therefore, a comprehensive understanding of emissivity variations in high temperatures is crucial for optimizing the performance of textured surfaces in solar receivers.

While various low-emissive coatings measured at room temperatures have been reported, extrapolating emissivity measured at room temperature is valid only if the emissivity of the coating does not have any temperature dependence in the required wavelength region [23]. He et al. calculated the emissivity at high temperatures by the weighted integration of the reflectance spectra measured at 82 °C and blackbody radiation at the corresponding temperature [24]. However, this method may underestimate the high-temperature emissivity. Many emissivity studies lack real-time assessment at high temperatures, limiting their practical relevance. The measurement of emissivity at working temperatures is the only way to accurately account for heat radiation losses, which in turn are needed to calculate the economic impact in the solar thermal plant design [23]. Real time emissivity studies of various multilayer and cermet coatings at different temperatures such as 327 °C [25], 400 °C [26], 500 °C [27–29], and 600 °C [30] have been reported in the literature. Yet, only a few reports are available on high temperature emissivity of coatings with absorber surfaces having micro/nano structures, e.g., emissivity of spinel coatings at temperatures from 800 °C to 1300 °C [31] and from 200 °C to 800 °C [32].

Texturing of steels and alloys is a method to improve absorptivity by methods such as etching and heat-treatment [33–35]. However, these studies were based on the naturally formed Cr and Fe oxide layer on steel which is very much prone to degradation at high temperature due to corrosion or peeling off [22,36–38]. Valkonen et. al. reported oxidation of steel at 900 °C to develop absorbing surfaces with absorptivity of 0.85-0.90 and emissivity of 0.10-0.20 [34]. However, details on the high temperature performance and real time spectral or angular dependent emissivity studies were not provided for these type of samples. Existing studies on the oxidation of steels and alloys primarily cover various applications such as reactor vessel alloys, heat-transfer material, etc. along with examining the dependence of emissivity on roughness and oxide thickness [22,39–42]. On the other hand, Si-based coatings, known for their relatively low emissivity have emerged as a promising material for solar thermal systems. The diffusion coefficient of steel alloying elements: Fe, Cr, Mn, and Ni in Fe and Fe-based alloys at high temperatures was found to be of the order of 10^{-5} cm²/s [43,44]. Whereas, the diffusion coefficients of Si in selected cases at high temperatures were found to be in the range of 10^{-13} - 10^{-15} cm²/s [45,46]. Depositing a Si layer on a steel substrate, followed by a heat treatment leads to the formation of various intermetallic compounds inside and on top of the Si matrix due to differences in diffusion rates between Si, Fe, Cr and other elements. These formations can influence the material's optical properties and thermal stability, while also affecting the overall microstructure of the coating. This aspect of Si/SS coating at high temperature has not been thoroughly explored for photothermal applications. Additionally, the literature currently lacks investigations of the angular and temperature-dependent emissivity of these surfaces in the context of concentrated solar power systems. Therefore, our work aims to address this gap by providing a thorough investigation of *in situ* angular and high-temperature emissivity properties of absorbers

developed by heat treatment of Si-deposited steel to evaluate its feasibility in the application of solar thermal systems.

In previous research, we have explored potential of thermal-treatment procedure of Si-deposited stainless steel (SS, grade AISI304) in achieving a textured surface absorber [18,19]. The diffusion of substrate elements (viz., Fe, Cr and Mn) through the Si layer (verified through cross-sectional TEM studies) forms nano- micro-islands on the surface and nanocrystallites inside the Si layer, thus reducing reflectance to below 10 % [18,19]. This nano-microstructured surface proved to be a promising cost-effective selective solar absorber, with a high absorptivity of 0.92 at room temperature and an emissivity value of 0.37 at 82 °C. However, this emissivity is semi-hemispherical (henceforth denoted as ϵ_{82}) and also not measured at actual operating temperatures. In this work, our primary objective is to understand how the radiative properties of a Si-deposited stainless steel surface evolve when prepared under different annealing temperatures. Moreover, we have evaluated the directional and hemispherical emissivities of those samples when exposed to temperatures between 200 °C and 700 °C, which are crucial for assessing the performance of samples under practical operating conditions. The emissivity is measured in real time at different temperatures. Unlike the cases where high-temperature emissivity is calculated from the room temperature emissivity theoretically, we report actual experimental data collected in situ, thereby showing the potential of our samples for high-temperature applications.

2. Experimental section

2.1. Sample preparation

A thin layer of Si (250 nm) was deposited on clean SS304 substrates (30 mm × 30 mm × 2 mm) using a top-down magnetron sputtering system with a pulsed direct current (DC) power supply. Prior to the Si layer deposition, SS304 stainless steel substrates were rigorously cleaned, which involved mechanical polishing to enhance surface smoothness.

Subsequently, these substrates were subjected to mirror polishing using 1.5 μm diamond paste to eliminate any remaining surface scratches. Following the polishing steps, the samples were ultrasonically cleaned in acetone and isopropyl alcohol for 15 min to remove any remaining oil or grease. Afterwards, they were dried and subjected to a final cleaning process within the sputtering system. The sputtering chamber was subsequently evacuated to an initial pressure of 5.0×10^{-6} mbar using rotary and turbomolecular pumps. For the sputter cleaning of the substrate, the argon flow rate and direct current (DC) bias voltage were kept at 15 sccm and -600 V, while the working pressure was 6.0×10^{-3} mbar. The Si deposition followed the substrate cleaning process, wherein a Si target of 3 inch (0.076 m) diameter (99.9 % purity) was used. The deposition was conducted at a target power of 75 W for 12 min at a working pressure of 2.6×10^{-3} mbar and Ar flow rate of 20 sccm. After developing the coating, the samples were introduced directly into an air furnace, which was maintained at various temperatures ranging from 700 °C to 1100 °C. Following a short annealing period of 2 – 3 min, the samples were extracted from the furnace and rapidly cooled to room temperature in the ambient air [18]. These samples have been labelled according to the respective annealing temperatures, such that a sample prepared at 700 °C is referred to as “S-700”, and so forth.

2.2. Assessment of optical properties

2.2.1. Measurements at room temperature

To assess the absorptivity values of the prepared samples, a solar spectrum reflectometer (Devices and Services, model SSR) was employed, with the incident angle set at 20° from the surface normal and a tungsten halogen light as source. Four wavelength detectors were used (UV, blue, red, and NIR) and the average of this was taken as the actual reflectance. This was used to calculate absorptivity. Emissivity measurements were conducted at 82 °C using an emissometer (Devices & Services, Model AE). Before

conducting high-temperature emissivity measurements, a UV-Vis-NIR spectrophotometer (Agilent, Cary 7000 UMS) equipped with an integrating sphere (internal diameter of 110 mm) was utilized to evaluate the reflectivity spectra of the as-deposited coatings at room temperature (RT) with an incidence angle of 8° . In the mid-infrared range, total reflectivity spectra (including both specular and diffuse components) were acquired by means of an Infragold-coated Bruker A 562-G integrating sphere using a Bruker IFS 66v/S FTIR spectrophotometer equipped with a DLaTGS detector. Both sets of reflectivity data were again collected after conducting the high-temperature emissivity measurements.

2.2.2. Directional and hemispherical emissivity measurements

The spectral emissivity measurements were performed using the HAIRL emissometer, which consists of a Fourier Transform Infrared (FTIR) spectrometer (Bruker Vertex v80), a vacuum sample chamber, a reference blackbody (Isotech Pegasus 970R), and an optical entrance box that offers switching between the blackbody source and the sample chamber by rotating a plane mirror [47]. The emissometer is equipped with a sample holder coupled to a rotating axis, which allows directional emissivity measurements from $\theta = 10^\circ$ to $\theta = 80^\circ$ with respect to the normal direction of the sample surface. The FTIR is equipped with a DLaTGS detector, which allows measurements in the $2\ \mu\text{m}$ to $25\ \mu\text{m}$ spectral range. After performing the reflectivity measurements, type K thermocouples were spot-welded at 5 mm each from the center of the sample for high-temperature emissivity measurements. The samples were placed individually inside the sample chamber and a vacuum level of 5.0×10^{-4} mbar was reached at room temperature. Directional emissivity measurements were performed from 200 °C to 700 °C every 100 °C and from $\theta = 10^\circ$ to $\theta = 80^\circ$ every 10° once the temperature was stabilized. Directional spectral emissivity and total hemispherical emissivity can be calculated by the equations reported in previous literature [32,48]. The temperature profile as a function of the time for the whole process is given in supplementary files (Fig. S1).

2.3 Structural and morphological characterization

X-ray diffraction (XRD) data were collected on an X'PERT diffractometer in θ - 2θ geometry with a Cu anode (Cu- K_{α} , $\lambda = 1.5405980 \text{ \AA}$) before and after the emissivity measurements. The diffractograms were acquired from 10° up to 80° in 2θ with a step size of 0.026° and an acquisition time of 97.9 s. The surface morphology of the as-prepared samples and corresponding elemental study were observed by FESEM (Carl Zeiss, Supra 40VP) and Energy Dispersive X-Ray Analysis (Oxford, INCA- PentaFETx3), respectively. The high-temperature annealed samples were investigated using a JEOL JSM-6400 scanning electron microscope (SEM) equipped with a W filament and an INCA EDX detector X-sight Series Si (Li) pentaFET Oxford with Be window. Secondary and backscattered electron images were acquired to characterize the surface of the samples. In addition, energy dispersive X-ray analysis (EDS) was performed to investigate the chemical composition. The operating voltage was 20 kV at a working distance of 15 mm and a beam current of 1 nA for the EDX analyses. The surface roughness was studied on a $20 \mu\text{m} \times 20 \mu\text{m}$ area using atomic force microscopy (AFM Anton Parr Tritech).

3. Results and discussion

3.1. Optical properties and morphology of textured Si on SS surface

In this section, we have focused on the properties of Si deposited samples that were subjected to annealing at various temperatures ranging from 700°C to 1100°C (S-700 to S-1100). Fig. 1(a) shows schematically the textured surface preparation process through sputtering of Si on SS, followed by air annealing, and subsequently rapid cooling. The evolution of absorptivity (α), emissivity (ϵ_{82}), and root mean square (RMS) roughness with increasing sample preparation temperatures is shown in Fig. 1(b). This emissivity was measured at 82° . S-700 and S-800 exhibit at room temperature similar and low absorptivity

of 0.54 and 0.58 and low emissivity of 0.17 and 0.21, respectively. The sample annealed at 900 °C (S-900) shows a maximum absorptivity of 0.92 with an emissivity of 0.37. On preparing the samples at 900 °C with lower or higher time intervals (<2 min or > 3 min) a lower absorptivity was observed. The samples prepared at lower temperatures had lower emissivity, however, the absorptivity was also low (e.g., at $t = 1$ min, $\alpha = 0.80$, $\varepsilon_{82} = 0.16$). When the annealing time was increased, absorptivity decreased and emissivity increased (e.g., at $t = 7$ min, $\alpha = 0.88$, $\varepsilon_{82} = 0.40$). Hence the time period of ~ 3 min was used for all samples. Further increase in annealing temperatures to 1000 °C and 1100 °C results in a declining trend in absorptivity, while their emissivity shows a minor increase. This change in absorptivity and emissivity as a function of annealing temperature appears to be related to roughness and follows the variation pattern in roughness till 1000 °C [49]. Samples S-700 and S-800 with RMS roughness values of 2.9 nm and 4.0 nm, respectively, exhibit lower absorptivity and emissivity than the others. In contrast, S-900 and S-1000 having a roughness of 84 nm and 102 nm, respectively show higher absorptivity and emissivity. An increase in roughness reduced solar reflectivity, leading to higher absorptivity. S-1100, however, does not follow this behavior. The large increase in RMS roughness (269 nm) reduces the absorptivity and slightly increases the emissivity. This shows that while the roughness increases absorptivity, it is not the only parameter that affects absorptivity. The emissivity however increases as roughness increases.

Fig. 1(c) shows the reflectivity spectra of all as-prepared samples in the UV-Vis-NIR and mid IR region, with the AM 1.5 solar spectrum and blackbody emission at 700 °C as a reference. The samples S-700 and S-800 exhibit high reflectivity in the solar spectrum, resembling thin film interference patterns of as-deposited Si on SS with three distinct minima at around 0.7 μm , 1.0 μm and 3.3 μm [18,50]. S-800 shows slightly lower reflectivity than S-700. However, these spectral characteristics are undesirable for efficient absorber materials.

Between 1.2 μm and 6 μm , Si is transparent to photons, allowing incident radiation to interact with the SS304 substrate without hindrance, leading to interference between the reflected radiations from Si and SS304 [51]. These interference patterns in the spectra of S-700 and S-800 confirm that annealing at 700 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ and 800 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ did not significantly modify the surface and composition of the Si layer, which is also evident from FESEM images in Fig. 1(d) and (e) (see comments below in this section). Notably, S-900 and S-1000 exhibit reflectivity spectra without any minima, indicative of increased roughness by micro/nanostructuring and chemical modification formed through annealing at temperatures higher than 800 $^{\circ}\text{C}$ [50]. These surfaces effectively suppress the reflectivity, diminish the interference effect and thereby improve light absorption. In addition to that, formation of some of the Si-based composition, being semiconducting in nature could possibly enhance the absorption in solar spectrum [52]. Altogether, these factors lead to low reflectivity around or lower than 0.1 in the 0.2 μm to 2 μm region, a substantial portion of the solar spectrum, making them promising solar absorber coatings. However, sample S-1100 shows a slightly increased solar reflectivity, possibly could be attributed to a significant increase in surface roughness that contributes to scattered solar reflection, thereby reducing solar absorption.

For the opaque samples, according to Kirchhoff's law, the emissivity of a surface can be computed as $\varepsilon = 1 - R$, where R is the reflectivity. In the mid-infrared range (from 2.5 μm to 20 μm), S-700 and S-800 show high reflectivity up to 80 % in Fig. 1(c). S-900 and S-1000 show a sharp cut-off around 2.5 μm between low and high reflectivity (high and low emissivity), showing spectral selectivity. Distinct peaks around 9 μm correspond to the absorption from Si and O bonds, suggesting formation of Si-based oxide [53]. An additional peak at 7.3 μm is observed for S-1000, likely from C – O bonds [54]. These variations in the reflectivity pattern and presence of different peaks suggest variation in the morphology and composition of the surface of investigated samples (Fig. S2).

These observations are supported by the top-view FESEM morphology and composition of the samples shown in Fig. 1(d-h) and Fig. S2. Sample S-700 exhibits (Fig. 1(d)) a smooth surface, explaining interference-induced reflectivity (Fig. 1(c)) of unaffected annealed Si film. Morphological changes initiate at 800 °C (Fig. 1(e)), revealing clusters of small structures composed of Fe, Cr, and/or Mn oxides and silicides (EDX data given in Fig. S2). In S-800, the smooth Si film between clusters contribute significantly to the evolution of the reflectivity spectra as it retains a thin film interference pattern. S-900 and S-1000 exhibit substantial morphological changes, as shown in Fig. 1(f) and Fig. 1(g), featuring structures (oxides and silicides) arranged in compact orders resembling an array of nano-micro texture. Effectively, these structures act as multiple particles with complex geometries separated by small gaps, inducing near-field enhancement and large absorption cross-section. Additionally, air-structure combination on the surface may act as a graded index medium, providing anti reflection properties [14,55–57]. The morphology of the samples prepared at 900 °C for 1 min showed islands that are distributed scarcely (Fig. S3(a)). For the sample prepared at 7 min, the gaps were almost non-existent (Fig. S3(b)). This further emphasizes the importance of the arrangement of the islands formed on the surface in absorptivity. When the islands are separated by gaps in the range of 0.25 – 3 μm (as in the case of Si-900 and Si-1000), the absorptivity is maximum. Thus, this arrangement is more crucial than roughness. Lastly, sample S-1100 shows distinctive irregular, rough, and degraded morphology with larger spacing between structures. This leads the light to scattered away in the larger gaps leading to reduced absorptivity compared to Si-900 and Si-1000 (Fig. 1(h)).

Above observations could mean that the diffusion of substrate elements onto the surface starts at 800 °C and is most prominent in S-900 and S-1000 samples. Referring the cross-sectional TEM data in previous reports [19], it can be inferred that the underlying Si rich layer exists in S-700 to S-1000 samples. However, in S-1100 sample, the underlying Si

rich layer may not be existing which is apparent from Fig. 1(h) and Fig. S2. In conclusion, the Si layer acts as a barrier of the free diffusion of substrate elements, thus, eliminating the formation of a uniform oxide cluster (as in the case of heat-treated SS substrate) [18]. Instead, it restricts diffusion to certain regions, which in turn results in the formation of nano-micro islands. The area of these diffusion regions increases as the temperature is increased from 800 °C to 1100 °C. The distribution of the nano-micro-islands is more compact and most beneficial for absorption when heat-treated at 900 °C or 1000 °C as the combination offers a refractive index gradient preventing reflection from refractive index mismatch.

3.2. High-temperature emissivity study on textured heat-treated Si layers

3.2.1. Directional spectral emissivity as a function of viewing angles

We conducted an in-depth analysis of the directional spectral emissivity across various emission angles in the wavelength range from 3 μm to 22 μm . Fig. 2(a-c) depicts the angular dependence of spectral emissivity for samples S-800, S-900, and S-1000 at 700 °C, respectively (directional emissivity spectra of other samples at other temperatures are given in Fig S3 and S4). Although experiments were done from 200 °C to 700 °C, emphasis was put on the measurements at 700 °C, considering the intended high temperature in solar thermal applications of the nanostructured coatings. Each sample goes through a thermal process for about 15 h, as emissivity is measured in real time at these temperatures (Fig. S1). All samples display two distinct behaviors where emissivity decreases with increasing angle below $\sim 8 \mu\text{m}$ and a complete reversal of this pattern in the long wavelength region. This shows a transition from dielectric to metallic character. With an increase in sample preparation temperature from 800 °C to 1000 °C, there is an observable increase in directional spectral emissivity in the lower wavelength region (below 8 μm) for all angles ($\theta = 10^\circ$ to $\theta = 70^\circ$). For example, at $\lambda = 4 \mu\text{m}$ and a viewing angle of 10° , emissivity increases from 0.62 in S-800 to 0.67 in S-900 and further to 0.77 in S-1000 (Fig. 2(a-c)). This trend

correlates with an increase in the refractive index of the medium [58], attributed to oxide and silicide formation due to thermal treatment. Sample S-800 exhibits a relatively uniform emission curve (Fig. 2(a)), while S-900 and S-1000 show noticeable absorption bands (Fig. 2(b) and Fig. 2(c)), possibly due to vibrational modes of different oxygen bonds with Si and other substrate elements [51]. The low emissivity of all samples in mid IR region suggests that the top layer (oxide/silicide) is almost transparent for this wavelength and the radiation is reflected by the metallic substrate. At around 22 μm , all samples exhibit similar emissivity values for a constant viewing angle due to the predominant contribution of radiation from the steel substrate. Interestingly, a pronounced shift in angular dependency becomes evident around 7 μm and 10 μm , with directional emissivity decreasing with increasing observation angle in wavelengths shorter than 7 μm and exhibiting the opposite trend for wavelengths longer than 10 μm . Directional emissivity of all samples measured on other temperatures (200 to 700 $^{\circ}\text{C}$) are presented in Fig. S4 and Fig. S5.

To provide better visualization of the aforementioned spectral and angular properties, directional spectral emissivity at specific wavelengths has been presented for S-800, S-900, and S-1000 in Fig. 2(d-f) (similar studies for S-700 and S-1100 are shown in Fig. S6). All samples exhibit a similar declining trend in emissivity up to 8-9 μm , with S-1000 showing the sharpest decrease. The emission from this region is hence predominantly from the dielectric part of the sample. At viewing angles from 60 $^{\circ}$ to 80 $^{\circ}$, the directional emissivity corresponding to shorter wavelengths decreases rapidly. For all viewing angles (except at 80 $^{\circ}$), directional emissivity remains nearly constant for one specific wavelength (e.g, 8 μm in S-800 and 12 μm in Si-1000). Beyond that point, a transition occurs, with emissivity increasing as the emission angle increases and reaching a maximum around 70 – 80 $^{\circ}$. In this region, the predominant interaction occurred with the metallic substrate surface leads to an angular dependence characteristic of metallic surfaces [40,59]. The transition wavelength,

where emissivity becomes angle-independent, corresponds to the boundary between the light absorbing and infrared reflecting behavior of the sample. This boundary shifts to longer wavelengths from S-800 to S-1000, indicating an evolution of the surface due to the oxidation and thus provoking a more dielectric behavior in the infrared emission spectra [51].

3.2.2. Thermal emissivity as a function of measurement temperature

Fig. 3(a-c) represents the directional spectral emissivity of S-800, S-900, and S-1000, at temperatures ranging from 200 °C to 700 °C, with a constant viewing angle of 10°, i.e., near-normal emission direction. A similar comparison for S-700 and S-1100 at 700 °C is shown in Fig. S6. Fig. 3(a) reveals that S-800 exhibits lower emissivity values from 200 °C to 600 °C, followed by a sudden increase at 700 °C. Interestingly, the emissivity of S-800 at 700 °C is similar to that of S-900 across the entire wavelength range, despite their different preparation conditions. Prolonged exposure to 700 °C during emissivity measurements may have affected the surface morphology, composition, or interfacial nanostructure of S-800, resulting in a spectrum similar to those observed for S-900 in Fig. 3(b). In contrast, both S-900 and S-1000 maintain nearly constant directional emissivity when increasing temperature, indicating thermal stability (Fig. 3(b) and Fig. 3(c)). For S-900 and S-1000, the presence of oxides/silicides leading to higher surface roughness collectively contributes to higher emissivities. However, at longer wavelengths, the SS substrate's (metallic) influence on the emissivity increases, resulting in a higher infrared reflection and lower emissivity within MIR range [14,41,60]. A consistent dip at approximately 8.5 μm , observed for S-900 and S-1000, resembles the minima present in quartz [61], while S-800 does not have such characteristic feature, indicating absence of detectable crystalline SiO_2 . EDX analysis reveals an increase in Cr, Mn, Fe based oxides and silicides content with higher sample preparation temperature, resulting in different optical properties (Fig. S2).

The near-normal (at a 10° emission angle) spectral emissivity shown in Fig. 3(d) for all samples at 700 °C corroborates the observation in Fig. 3(a-c) (comparison at other temperatures are shown in Fig. S7). The emissivity increases from S-700 to S-1100 at higher wavelengths (>6 μm) with a rise in sample preparation temperature. Noticeably, S-1100 spectra exhibit a peak near 10 μm, reminiscent of peaks reported for Cr-Mn oxides [62,63], suggesting a possible compositional difference between S-1100 and samples S-900 and S-1000 (Fig. S2).

Fig. 3(e) illustrates the evolution of the hemispherical emissivity and near normal emissivity (at 10° angle) of S-900 sample with varying measurement temperature. A noticeable increase in both emissivity values is observed as the temperature rises, ranging from 0.44 at 200 °C to 0.59 at 700 °C (for hemispherical emissivity). This finding indicates that measuring high-temperature normal/hemispherical emissivity is essential to assess the inaccuracies that may arise when extrapolating data obtained at room temperature or at 82 °C (ϵ_{82} data shown in Fig. 3(e)). The continuous rise in emissivity can be attributed to surface modifications, as well as a shift in the weight distribution of the Planck function towards higher spectral emissivity with an increase in temperature.

Although terms like normal emissivity and hemispherical emissivity are often used interchangeably, their values can vary based on the material properties [64]. In this particular case, there is a relatively good agreement between the two. The slightly higher values of near normal emissivity could be because of the two different regions below and above ~8 μm showing opposite angular dependencies to emissivity, thereby cancelling the effect of each other in the hemispherical emissivity.

The variation in hemispherical emissivity of all samples with temperature (Fig. 3(f)) is also studied. From 500 °C to 700 °C, the hemispherical emissivity of S-900, S-1000, and S-1100 increases only by a small margin. For 500 °C and 600 °C, the hemispherical

emissivity is lower for S-700 and S-800 than the other samples but at 700 °C it increases sharply, approaching the value of the other three samples. Hence, S-700 and S-800 do not offer any advantage for high temperature applications due to their low absorptive property and low thermal stability of emissivity.

3.3. Structural, morphological, and optical properties after high-temperature emissivity measurements

High-temperature emissivity measurements can be considered equivalent to subjecting the samples to high-temperature annealing (Fig. S1), making it essential to investigate changes in various material properties following emissivity measurements. Fig. 4(a) presents XRD analysis of the S-800, S-900, and S-1000, conducted both before and after the emissivity studies. All substrate peaks are marked as X (austenite phase) and Y (ferrite phase) against (111), (200) and (220) planes of austenite (ICDD: 00-033-0397) and (110) plane for ferrite (ICDD: 00-001-1262). Additional peaks, marked as A, B, and C, respectively (A = X_3O_4 , B = X_2O_3 , X is Fe, Cr, and/or Mn, C = silicides) are also identified (Table 1). The XRD pattern of oxides and silicides with the same crystal structure exhibits similar peak positions due to the comparable atomic size of transition metals, making unique identification challenging. Possible matching details are provided in supplementary information (Table S1, Fig. S8).

Fig. 4(a) shows that prior to emissivity measurements, S-800 does not exhibit any detectable oxide peaks but showed presence of Fe based silicide peaks (ICDD: 00-042-1329 and 01-071-1110). However, after the emissivity measurements, additional silicide peaks have appeared, evidencing formation of new phases after thermal exposure. No oxide peaks were observed for Si-800. Hence the increased emissivity in Si-800 at 700 °C could be also due to increased roughness due to formation of new nano-microstructures of silicides. It has been reported that the increased Si content in Fe-Si phase leads to increased electrical

resistivity which means more dielectric nature than metallic nature [65]. Hence, the increased emissivity could be also due to the increased dielectric nature of the top layer of Si-800. The XRD data obtained prior to the emissivity measurements of samples S-900 and S-1000 reveal the presence of oxides as well as silicides in the samples. Importantly, even after performing the emissivity measurements, all identified peaks remained unchanged for both samples, indicating the absence of a new phase. These findings suggest that these samples are structurally stable at temperatures up to 700 °C.

The reflectivity spectra of S-800, S-900, and S-1000 before and after emissivity measurements are given in Fig. 4(b-d). Notably, a significant change is evident for S-800 (Fig. 4(b)), which is in agreement with the evolution seen in the emissivity measurements, where interference minima disappear post-emissivity measurement. However, the second spectrum of S-800 resembles those of S-900, exhibiting lower reflectivity in the solar spectrum. On the other hand, the reflectivity spectra of S-900 and S-1000 (Fig. 4(c) and (d), respectively) remain unchanged even after exposure to 700 °C during emissivity measurements.

Further confirmation of the changes in S-700 and S-800 and the stability of the other three samples are observed in Fig. 5 from the initial and final backscattered electron images of all samples. The initial image of S-700 shows a homogenous surface with no contrast difference. S-700 retains to a certain extent the appearance even after emissivity measurements. Small dark regions appear which could be silicides of the substrate elements (Fe, Cr, and Mn) as they have higher contrast than the nearby Si region. These were not detectable in XRD. S-800 develops a different surface morphology after the emissivity measurements at 700 °C. In the initial images, the surface consists of scarcely scattered islands of nano-microstructures (dark regions in Fig 5(b)). After the emissivity was measured, however, the diffusion of substrate elements and subsequent silicide formation occurs on

majority of the surface. This is in agreement with the observations made from emissivity and reflectivity spectra of S-800 at/after 700 °C. Since the emissivity measurements were carried out in vacuum, the O concentration during measurement was low. In the absence of O in the chamber, the substrate elements diffused out to form majorly silicide islands in S-800. Still the reflectivity spectra of S-800 showed resemblance to that of S-900. S-900 had both oxide and silicide islands formed on the surface even before emissivity measurements. This suggests that rather than the composition (silicides or oxides), it is the distribution of the islands and the underlying Si-rich region which improves the optical properties. In contrast, S-900 and S-1000 maintained their morphological micro/nanotextured features. These samples have a uniform distribution of the dark and bright regions due to the almost periodic array of smaller islands of Fe, Cr, and Mn oxides/silicides. Besides, S-1100 retains its morphology. However, there appears to be compositional change as observed from the contrast difference.

Despite having a slightly higher emissivity, S-900 and S-1000 samples exhibit remarkable thermal stability, enduring temperatures as high as 700 °C for longer duration (Fig. S1). The sample preparation involved heat treatment in air at 900 °C and 1000 °C, leading to the formation of stable nano-microstructured islands that exhibit stability at relatively lower temperatures. This exceptional stability can be attributed to several factors. Firstly, the intrinsic thermal stability of SS304 as a substrate plays a crucial role. Additionally, when exposed to elevated temperatures, the samples form protective stable oxides and silicide such as, Fe_3O_4 , Cr_2O_3 , Cr_2MnO_4 , Fe_3Si , and Fe_2MnSi , which remain stable at high temperatures [66,67]. These stable compounds of transition metals and Si promote absorption mechanisms at lower wavelengths and form surface textures that suppress the reflection, thus acting as antireflective layer [68]. Overall, the straightforward approach involving thermal treatment and subsequent cooling of Si coated SS enables

effective tailoring of micro/nanostructure, surface roughness, composition, and desired emissive properties in a wide wavelength range at elevated temperatures.

The importance of the current work can be understood on comparing it with literature. One of the major advantages of this work is the cost-effective sample preparation method. Simple intrinsic absorbers often need additional antireflection layers to obtain competitive absorptivity [69–74]. Even with an antireflective layer, the emissivity of these coatings was reported at 25 °C - 100 °C [69,70,72–74]. Some of the tandem coatings have reported emissivity at up to 500 °C, however, the absorptivity of these samples was less than 0.80 [75,76]. Several multilayer coatings have been reported to have very low emissivity (<0.11) along with high absorptivity (>0.94) [26,77,78]. The drawback of these coatings is their thermal stability. These coatings report emissivity measurements maximum up to 400 °C and also their thermal stability is restricted to >550 °C. These coatings also are not cost-effective as they need multiple sputtering targets for different layers. This work reports in situ emissivity studies up to 700 °C. While the emissivity of the samples studied here is slightly higher than reported values, the sample makes up for it with the stability of emissivity at higher temperatures. Compared to the coatings mentioned above, the samples studied in this work are far superior in terms of cost-effectiveness and thermal stability of emissivity.

4. Conclusions

In this work, we demonstrate experimentally that the annealing and the subsequent cooling of Si thin films on stainless steel substrates across a temperature range from 700 °C to 1100 °C significantly influence absorptivity, emissivity, and surface morphology. The transition from smooth surfaces (such as the surface of sample S-700) to nano-microstructured surfaces (as in samples S-900 and S-1000) enhances light absorption. Directional spectral emissivity experiments confirm the decrease in emissivity with increasing observation angle (from 10° to 80°) for shorter wavelengths ($\lambda < 6 \mu\text{m}$) and the

opposite trend for longer wavelengths ($\lambda > 12 \mu\text{m}$) in the mid-infrared range. It also exhibits a consistent wavelength dependence, manifesting a transition from a dielectric to a metallic nature. This transition is attributed to contributions from both silicon (Si) and the underlying metallic stainless steel (SS) substrate. Additionally, an increase in directional spectral emissivity over a wide wavelength range is observed for S-700 to S-1100. The study also highlights the evolution of hemispherical and total directional emissivity with varying measurement temperature (from 200 °C to 700 °C), showing a consistent increase in emissivity attributed to surface modifications, oxide/silicide formation due to substrate ion diffusion and shift of the Planck function weight distribution towards higher spectral emissivity regions when temperature increases. High-temperature emissivity measurements do not induce change in structural, morphological and optical properties of S-900 and S-1000 samples, showcasing their remarkable thermal endurance up to 700 °C. Overall, this unconventional sample preparation method demonstrates significant potential for preparing promising solar absorbers like S-900 and S-1000, which are suitable for high temperature applications.

Table 1: Peak details for the XRD patterns acquired for all samples.

Symbol	Compound	ICDD
X	Substrate SS304	00-033-0397
	(Fe-austenite)	
Y	Substrate SS304	00-001-1262
	(Fe-ferrite)	
A	Fe ₃ O ₄	01-086-1350
	Cr ₂ MnO ₄	01-075-1614
B	Fe ₂ O ₃	01-084-0311
	Cr ₂ O ₃	00-038-1479
C	Fe ₃ Si	00-042-1329
	Fe ₂ MnSi	01-071-1110

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Fig. 1: a) Schematic representation of sample preparation, b) variation of roughness, absorptivity, and emissivity (ϵ_{82} , measured using an emissometer) as a function of sample preparation temperature, c) AM 1.5 solar spectrum, blackbody radiation at 700 °C and UV-Vis-NIR and IR reflectivity spectra of as-prepared samples at room temperature prior to emissivity measurements and FESEM secondary electron top-view images of samples d) S-700, e) S-800, f) S-900, g) S-1000, and h) S-1100 taken before emissivity measurements.

Fig. 2: Directional spectral emissivity of samples S-800, S-900, and S-1000 measured at 700 °C a-c) as a function of wavelength and d-f) as a function of emission angle at four different wavelengths.

Fig. 3: Near normal spectral emissivity (at 10° angle) measured at different temperatures for samples a) S-800, b) S-900, and c) S-1000, d) near normal spectral emissivity (at 10° angle) for all samples measured at 700 °C, e) hemispherical emissivity and directional emissivity at 10° angle (near normal) of S-900 at different temperatures and f) evolution of hemispherical emissivity of all samples with temperature (500 °C - 700 °C).

Fig. 4: a) XRD data of sample S-800, S-900 and S-1000 before and after emissivity measurements (details of the compounds A, B, C, X, and Y are given in Table 1). UV-Vis-NIR and IR reflectivity spectra before and after emissivity measurements of sample b) S-800, c) S-900, and d) S-1000.

Fig. 5: SEM backscattered electron top-view images taken a-e) before and f-j) after emissivity measurements for all samples.

Fig. 1

Fig. 2

Fig. 3

Fig. 4

Fig. 5

